

Information Seeking Behavior Models

- **Definition of Information Seeking Behavior**

Information Seeking behavior refers to the method a user uses to obtain the information they require. As part of the user's approach, all potential sources of information are identified, and the best one is chosen. Information seeking is an activity that is motivated by a user's need to fulfill a certain objective. In addition, Case states that information seeking is "a deliberate attempt to obtain information in response to a need or gap in your knowledge" (Case, 2008). Users' methods for creating, exchanging, and locating information that is relevant to their information needs are all included in information seeking behavior. The user may use computerized information systems or more traditional information sources (such books, magazines, libraries, etc.) while seeking information. Understanding user information needs and searching patterns is crucial for building library collections, improving existing products and services, and establishing new services to satisfy user information demands.

- **Information Seeking Behavior Models: -**

Most models of information-seeking conduct are claims that attempt to explain an information-seeking behavior, its causes and consequences, or the relationships between several phases of information-seeking behavior. however they are at a pre-theoretical level, few models even go so far as to discover connections between theoretical concepts, however they might point to connections that are worth looking into or testing. However, there appear to be fewer models of information behavior than models that concentrate on information-seeking behavior or information searching. Every model has been looked at independently. Information seeking models are discussed below.....

➤ **Wilson’s Model of Information Behaviour (1981):**

The information user, who has a specific information need, is at the top of the Wilson model. By placing demands on information systems, such as a library catalog or other information sources—basically anything that isn't made especially for information retrieval—the requirement is what motivates users to engage in information-seeking behavior. They can then determine if the demand was successful, such as having been met, or unsuccessful. If the demand was successful, they now have useful information. The procedure can be restarted with a new need if the information has met their needs. They can begin the procedure again with the same need if it hasn't been met. Information use can also result in other information-seeking behaviors, particularly information exchange, which in this context refers to sharing or requesting information from others rather than looking for information from systems or sources. Additionally, after they have information that they can utilize, they might be able to share it with others by knowledge transfer.

The major conclusion from this model is that the information user has a need and seeks information from outside sources to meet that need. Finally, it can be argued that information-seeking behavior can be much more flexible and less idealized than the strict examples of having a need, acting on that behavior, demanding success or failure, and then turning around. Wilson himself admits that another criticism is that it lacks any hypotheses or causal factors. For an example, consider the concept of an information requirement that leads to specific information behavior over another. As a result, nothing in this model can be tested directly; rather, it serves more as a general study map.

Fig1. **Wilson’s Model of Information Behaviour (1981)**

➤ **Wilson’s Model of Information Behaviour (1996):**

The person is once again at the heart of this modified model, which is a person-centered approach. To more deliberately add context into the model, they have now been named person in context rather than information user.

The scenario in which they require information is the context of the information that is required. The activation mechanism, which is essentially what prompts the user to begin attempting to satisfy that demand, is informed by this. By tying these theories to the activation mechanism, Wilson tries to solve the problem of his previous model's lack of causative components. Susan Folkman, a psychologist, developed the stress-slash-coping theory, which explains why certain needs will trigger an information search while others won't. Since we haven't yet incorporate the person's context, we may consider this first activate mechanism to be rather context independent. It just depends on the context of the information that is required. Now that the individual's information has been activated and the situational context has been taken into consideration. Next, we deal with the intervening variables, which are basically the context-related factors that have a favourable or negative impact on an individual's information behavior. In order to account for all components of context, Wilson classified them into psychological demographic role-related or interpersonal environmental and source qualities. as, we might essentially arrange these as we like. We are aware that we have taken into consideration both the situational and individual contexts. The second activating mechanism, which is what genuinely motivates the individual to engage in their information-seeking behavior, comes into play at that point. Wilson claims that the second mechanism was influenced by social learning theory, which incorporates the idea of self-efficacy—basically, whether or not an individual believes they will be able to carry out the search successfully—and risk-reward theory, which originates in the field of economics. Once more, these theories could be changed or replaced based on our opinions. The most crucial factors to consider are the effects on and potential explanations for the activating mechanisms. Intentional (such as active search) and unintentional (such as passive search) forms of searching have been included into the information-seeking behavior, which has shifted away from placing demands on systems.

The advantage of this model is that it arranges concept context in relation to information behavior rather than as an external factor. This means that it discusses how Will eventually leads to the information seeking behavior and how it influences it in a very deliberate manner rather than merely having an external factor influence it.

Fig2. Wilson’s Model of Information Behaviour (1996):

➤ **Elis's Model**

Ellis's model of information seeking behavior is a series of steps a user takes when looking for information. It describes how a user looks for and uses information. Information seeking process has the following steps: -

Starling: -

Starling indicates the starting of the information seeking process. For example, a user asks a knowledgeable person (Librarian, colleague, another user etc) about the information according to their information needs which means selection of sources for seeking the needed information asking knowledgeable persons.

Chaining: -

Chaining is to find and follow various links, citations or materials according to the information needed by the user. For example, if a user wants to know about a topic, he can find and follow the links, material according to that topic means observing the linking, such as citations, footnotes, and bibliographies, that were acquired from the original information sources.

Browsing: -

Browsing means sort of undirected or semi-structured searching to get specific information. For example, by using the short term of the topic or information that the user is looking for, the information on that topic can be found very easily. Simple browsing also includes looking through subject headings, lists of titles, tables of contents, and other forms of semi-structured or semi-directed searching.

Differentiating: -

Differentiating means specifying how information that is needed can be differentiated from other information as needed. For example, when a user is looking for a history book, he/she can get the exact information if he specifies whether he is looking for a modern or ancient history book. Differentiating the sources that were located according to the type and caliber of information they contain.

Monitoring: -

Monitoring means that the information or topic that users are interested in will keep coming. For example, if a user goes to OPAC and searches according to his/her topic or keyword-based search, the user will see the materials that contain his/her topic or keyword and the topic related materials will keep coming. And also Monitoring means tracking advancements in the user's area of interest example: - checking frequently for updates on fresh material from a variety of sources, including magazines, journals, newspapers, conferences, and more.

Extracting: -

Extracting is the process of choosing and identifying the most relevant topic or Information that is needed from a source means obtaining information from that source that satisfies needs. For example, When the user comes to the library, he is satisfied if he gets the information he needs.

Verifying: -

Verifying means checking whether the information is accurate. That is, to check whether the necessary information obtained from the source is correct. For example, when the user comes to ask for the information he/she needs, they check whether the information he/she came to ask for is given or how important or accurate that information is for him/her.

Ending: -

It could be characterized as "tying up loose ends" by conducting a last search. When the information search is finished and the user is happy with the information they have found, it is said to be ending.

Fig 3. **Elis's Model**

➤ **Kulthau's Model**

Kulthau's model was created based on how to search for information and how to write to find the information we need. Carol Kuhlthau mentions her model of teaching how to search. For example, when two users search for the same topic, Carol Kulthau mentioned the search process required to get information according to their topic. Besides, according to her, she felt the need for an orientation on how to search for information. For example, how a user will search through OPAC according to his/her information needs is said to be shown through orientation in this model. Task Initiation, Selection, Exploration, Formulation, Collection, and Presentation are the steps that are followed in the model to get the necessary data.

Task Initiation: - The first phase in the model is called "initiation," and it describes the moment a user decides it's time to start a task. At this point, the subject realizes how little he knew and feels quite nervous and uncertain.

Topic selection: - The user becomes somewhat aware of the area of interest or topic to observe and learn during the second stage, which is selection. And because the main area of interest is still unclear, the person feels less nervous but still uncertain.

Pre-focus exploration: - The third step is exploration, where the user discovers a topic they know a little bit about. As the person begins researching the subject, their level of worry and uncertainty decreases.

Focus formulation: - In the fourth step of the process, called formulation, the user selects the subject of interest to be further investigated and studied.

Information Collecting: - The fifth step is collecting, when the user gathers important data using a variety of search engines, gains a better understanding of the issue, and determines the path of the study. The user's level of confidence rises at this point.

Presentation: - The sixth step is presentation, where all of the information and data gathered are combined and given as a final report summarizing the whole information-gathering process. At this moment, if the user achieves his objective, the process is successful; if he fails or does not receive the necessary information, the user is greatly disappointed. The final step in this strategy is assessment, which deals with the user's self-evaluation and fosters more self-awareness and a sense of success.

Fig 4. Kulthau's Model

➤ Dervin's Model

According to Brenda Dervins, who developed the sense-making theory in 1983, it is more than just a model; it is "a set of assumptions, a theoretic perspective, a methodological approach, a research method, and a practice designed to cope up with information perceived as, —a human tool designed for making sense of a reality assumed to be both chaotic and orderly."

The four main components of the sense making model are as follows: the first is the situation in time and space, which represents the circumstances under which the need for information arises; the second is the gap, which represents the difference between the desired situation and the contextual situation; and the final result, which is the outcome of sense making and which narrows the gap between the situation and the outcome (Wilson, 1999). Strategies are used to build the bridge across the gap. The idea that all of the many information behavior types that have been identified may represent sense-making strategies—that is, methods used by an individual to maintain or create sense in an unpredictable world—is placed forward clearly here. People can seek information to fill the gap. They may change their internal reality in this way until it more closely matches what we refer to as "external reality." By modifying "external reality" to better fit their opinions, they can also bridge the divide. For example, a researcher who is creating a new theory or an individual who is facing allegations may decide to change what their community views as "true" or "acceptable." In this case, disseminating or arguing about information could be useful information behavior. A person may generate information to close the gap or build a bridge, depending on their personal goal. Ignoring the gap or keeping it small can be interpreted as avoiding information.

Fig 4. Dervin's Model

➤ Ingwersen's Model

In Kulthau's model, the search process could be started even if there is no idea about how to search for information on one's topic, but in Ingwersen's model, one must have an idea about how to find information on one's topic. It was originally based on how users searched from 1977 to 1991. Based on what questions they ask, what their query is about the topic, how they think, the report was created in 1992. Which essentially gave a holistic view of all interactive information retrieval. Ingwersen asserts that the following four concerns are essential to information retrieval—

- A. Every interactive communication process that takes place during an information retrieval process can be thought of as a cognitive process that can take place in any of the information-processing components.
- B. Any communication method between the sender and the recipient (human or machine) loses the underlying assumptions and intentionality of messages, which are essential for perception and comprehension.
- C. All acts of interpretation performed by the sender and the recipient are accompanied by uncertainties and unpredictabilities, which are inherent in information retrieval interactions.
- D. Only an individual user in context may truly retrieve information.

The following characteristics of information search and retrieval are suggested by Ingwersen's model:

- a) **Individual's cognitive search:** - An individual's cognitive space is defined by their work and interests, their current cognitive state, a difficulty or objective, uncertainty, and their information demands and behavior.
- b) **Social or Institutional Environment search:** - The domain, organizational strategies or goals, tasks, and preferences that define the social or organizational environment.

Wilson remarks that Ingwersen's model closely resembles the models of behavior related to information seeking. Example, Wilson's model's "person in context" and "environmental factors" sections are similar to the two components of "user's cognitive space" and "social/organizational environment."

➤ Fig 5. Ingwersen's Model

➤ **Belkin's Model**

According to Belkin and his colleagues' ASK (Anomalous States of Knowledge) model, an information-seeking process starts with a problem, but at first, neither the problem nor the information required to address it are completely understood. As a result, the information system should facilitate interactive search processes, and information searchers must go through an iterative process to formulate a search request. Belkin's AsK model states that before receiving information about a subject, an idea, a thought, is created in imagination about the subject and the idea is internal but not expressed. For example, the idea we think while writing a project eventually changes for some reason that remains hidden inside our mind.

Within the parameters of "goal of interaction," "mode of retrieval," and "resource considered," Belkin et al.'s episode model focuses on the steps taken throughout an information search, from scanning to searching. This model's idea is that people frequently use a variety of searching techniques during a series of information retrieval sessions. The four dimensions of "scanning to searching," "goal of interaction," "mode of retrieval," and "resource considered" allow Belkin's model to characterize any one information-seeking approach based on where it falls. To identify the actual information need, to understand the information need or seeking, to clarify what information is wanted and what is not wanted.

Fig6. Belkin's Model

➤ Saracevic's Model

In 1997, Saracevic made modifications to the stratified interaction model that he had introduced in 1996. The stratified interaction model's basic assumption is that people utilize information by interacting with information retrieval systems, and that information use is linked to situational applicability and cognition. Users and computers are the main components of the stratified model. The interface makes it possible to start a range of interactions, which can be thought of as a series of events taking place in multiple interconnected levels or strata, each involving distinct elements and/or particular processes. For example, processes may be physiological (such as visual, tactile, or auditory), psychological, or cognitive on the human side; they may be physical and symbolic on the computer side, and the interface facilitates surface-level interaction. Several things could be involved in the interaction, such as.....

- Through an interface, users can have a dialogue by giving orders and receiving responses, which are computer utterances. In addition to searching and matching, they may also do a variety of other "things," like understand and extracting the characteristics of a particular computer component or information resource; browsing and navigating within and among information resources, including distributed ones; assessing the status of a process, visualizing displays and results; and receiving and giving various forms of feedback.
- In a similar vein, computers communicate with users using predetermined procedures and "understandings" unique to the computer system, and they respond in this dialogue with predetermined answers; they may also produce requests for responses from the user.

The Saracevic model observes a few things

1. What the first user wants, what is his/her goal, where he/she could reach by getting information.
2. What results were obtained by retrieving information from the source or from the computer?
3. Through what process or what kind of search did you get the information.
4. How useful was the information obtained by the user or how useful was the process used to retrieve the information

This model is based on three different level

1. Cognitive
2. Affective
3. Situational

Fig 7. Saracevic's Model

➤ Bates's Model

According to Bates' berry-picking model for knowledge seeking, users' information demands and inquiries are always changing as a result of studying and gaining knowledge from the content they find through searches. According to the Berry-picking model, users' information demands are not met by the results of a specific search set, but rather by a sequence of choices and pieces of information discovered throughout the information search process.

According to Bates cascade model, each level of an information system communicates with every other the layer of the architecture. This cascade of connections ends at the interface, where all of the earlier connections have either produced components that serve multiple purposes or effective information retrieval. The cascade model for practical information retrieval systems is based on the fundamental idea that an information-retrieval system is certain to be substandard if its component levels are not all designed together. In this model, there are four levels.

- A. The framework, which includes databases, hardware, software, and networks, makes up the first level.
- B. The information or material and the metadata framework make up the second level.
- C. The information retrieval system beginning with accessible information through interface design accompanied by technological infrastructure is represented by the third layer.
- D. The human component of the technology, which includes user comprehension and purpose as well as search activity, makes up the fourth level.

Fig 8. Bates's Berry-picking Model

- **Conclusion: -**

Relevant to a study on information needs and information-seeking behavior are the definitions of information-seeking and information behavior models. The previous description makes clear that each model reflects a unique, however related or overlapping, approach to the study of information-seeking behavior. The Wilson model contributes to a better understanding of users' information behavior and offers the required basis for research on information user behavior. Kuhlthau's (1993) information process model and Ellis' (1989) model, on the other hand, describe how information users seek information. Understanding how information seekers approach information-finding can be aided by this description of the various information-seeking procedures, such as browsing or monitoring. Users' demand for knowledge in the context of their own circumstances is the main focus of Dervin's (1983) sense-making technique. This takes attention away from Ellis and Kuhlthau's descriptions of the information-seeking procedures. One thing that all of the models have in common is that using information is a multi-phase process. These stages include determining the information needs, deciding to use the information, choosing and obtaining information sources, locating and collecting the information, analysing and processing the information, and using the information. Utilizing the necessary information to finish a task is the result of the information-seeking process.

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